

Language Tandem and Intercultural Competence: Bridging Integration and Collaborative Learning between Spanish and Irish Students

Antonio Daniel Juan Rubio

Department of Language and Literature, University of Granada (Spain)

Mailing address: C/ Prof, Vicente Callao, 18011 Granada

Email: adjuanrubio@gmail.com

Received: Oct 02, 2025

Accepted: Nov 02, 2025

Published: Nov 06, 2025

Abstract

Learning a foreign language (FL) is a constant challenge in education, as there is often limited exposure to real-world environments, which affects the acquisition of linguistic and socio-cultural skills due to the limited input received (García-Sánchez & Orellana, 2021). According to Krashen (1982), language acquisition is most effective in a native environment, which contrasts with traditional approaches that may not be sufficient for meaningful learning. For this reason, this article proposes the implementation of a linguistic tandem between a Compulsory Secondary Education school (CSE) in Granada, Spain, and a school in Malahide, Ireland, to improve the language skills of students through interaction with native speakers.

Keywords: ELE, EFL, intercultural competence, language tandem, secondary education

1. INTRODUCTION

The idea for this research stems from the pressing need to address the difficulties students face in learning a second language as a foreign language (Bolívar Botía, 2021). Spanish students often struggle to acquire English due to a lack of oral practice and real-life situations, a problem also faced by Irish students (Martínez-Flor & Usó-Juan, 2022). Despite classroom lessons, the lack of exposure to the language hampers development, fluency, and listening comprehension. Moreover, the continued use of traditional methodologies, which focus on grammar and memorization rather than communicative strategies, further compounds the issue.

Another critical challenge is the lack of intercultural integration among students. Language teaching is about learning grammatical structures, going beyond, and understanding the cultural and social context (Pérez Cañado, 2021). However, current educational approaches often overlook this dimension, which can lead to difficulties in communication and a lack of understanding of linguistic details and their implications. In this sense, the absence of contact with native speakers and cultural immersion experiences hinders comprehensive language learning.

Implementing the linguistic tandem project is a direct response to these challenges. By facilitating direct communication between native students at both schools, this initiative promotes meaningful learning (Bueno Reyna & Alvarado Martínez, 2022). Students practice languages in real contexts with genuine communicative purposes. Interaction with native classmates enhances their language competence and boosts their motivation and self-confidence in speaking a foreign language. Furthermore, as a two-way linguistic exchange, students assume the roles of both learners and facilitators, fostering the co-construction of knowledge.

From a curricular perspective, the project is integrated into the educational programming of the centres to ensure that the tandem activities align with the learning objectives of both languages. Regarding methodology, active approaches such as project-based learning and gamification have been proposed, enabling students to engage more dynamically in language acquisition (Royo-Vela et al., 2023). Likewise, information and communication technologies (ICT) play a key role since digital platforms for video calls, forums, or educational social networks will facilitate interaction between students from both centres (Haleem et al., 2023; Holgado-Sáez & Díaz-Bravo, 2020).

From a socio-cultural perspective, the linguistic tandem encourages the development of intercultural competence (Redecker, 2023). By fostering direct contact with native speakers and encouraging participation in joint activities, this project significantly contributes to the students' understanding and appreciation of other communities' customs, traditions, and lifestyles. García-Sánchez and Orellana (2021) highlight that intercultural competence is vital in today's globalized world. By promoting such competence, the proposed project enhances the students' language skills and enriches their cultural understanding and global perspective.

To conclude, implementing a language tandem between a high school in Granada and a school in Malahide will enhance students' language skills and contribute to their personal and social development (Eurydice, 2022). Combining innovative methodological approaches with technology and intercultural interaction, this innovation project is an effective strategy to transform language teaching in both schools.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Given its impact on students' communicative competence and cultural integration, foreign language learning in educational contexts has been the subject of numerous studies in recent years. This educational innovation project is based on a theoretical framework that combines normative aspects, previous research, and similar innovative experiences. This review aims to justify the relevance and viability of the project in the current educational context.

2.1. Background

The learning of foreign languages has been the subject of numerous research and educational projects that have sought to optimize their teaching and improve the communicative competence of the students (Green, 2020). Over the past few decades, various methodologies have been implemented in different educational systems to address the limitations of the traditional approach, which is based on the explicit teaching of grammar and vocabulary memorization (Hamilton, 2021). This section reviews relevant background information on language teaching, using linguistic tandems, implementing active methodologies, and previous experiences such as the educational innovation proposal presented in this article.

In recent years, the focus of language teaching has shifted towards the development of communicative competence, emphasizing the ability of students to interact effectively and appropriately in real-life situations. This change has been influenced by the communicative approach, which prioritizes meaningful communication over rote memorization of linguistic forms. As a result, educators have explored new strategies that foster authentic language use, such as task-based learning, project-based learning, and content and language integrated learning (CLIL), which integrate language instruction with subject matter content (Holgado-Sáez & Díaz-Bravo, 2020).

One of the most innovative strategies that has gained prominence is the use of linguistic tandems. Tandem learning involves pairing students with native speakers of the target language, allowing both parties to practice and improve their language skills through mutual

exchange. This approach not only enhances linguistic competence but also promotes intercultural understanding and motivation, as learners are exposed to different perspectives and real communicative contexts (Bueno Reyna & Alvarado Martínez, 2022). The increasing availability of digital platforms has facilitated the implementation of virtual tandems, making it possible for students to interact with peers from around the world, regardless of geographical barriers.

Active methodologies have played a crucial role in transforming language education. Approaches such as cooperative learning, flipped classroom, and gamification encourage students to take an active role in their learning process (Freiermuth & Huang, 2021). These methods increase student engagement, foster autonomy, and create a more dynamic and participatory classroom environment. For instance, the integration of environmental topics into English language teaching through the Green English Language Teaching (GELT) approach not only improves language skills but also raises students' awareness of global issues, linking language learning with social responsibility (Abdel Latif, 2024).

Previous experiences with educational innovation have demonstrated that combining active methodologies with technological tools and collaborative strategies can lead to significant improvements in language acquisition. For example, the use of digital storytelling, online forums, and educational games has been associated with higher levels of motivation and better retention of vocabulary and grammatical structures. Moreover, adapting instruction to the diverse needs and learning styles of students has contributed to more inclusive and effective language teaching practices (Topal, 2024).

In summary, the evolution of FL teaching reflects a growing recognition of the need to move beyond traditional, teacher-centred methods. By incorporating linguistic tandems, active methodologies, and innovative educational experiences, educators can create more meaningful, motivating, and effective learning environments that better prepare students for the communicative demands of a globalized world (Elo & Pörn, 2021).

2.2. Use of linguistic tandems in language teaching

The concept of linguistic tandem is based on reciprocity and cooperation between two native speakers of different languages who exchange knowledge to improve their respective linguistic competencies (Wardak, 2024). This approach has been widely adopted in university settings and international exchange programs, where students can interact with native speakers in a natural and informal environment (Isaí Serrato Padilla Rodríguez, 2020).

Numerous studies have shown the benefits of tandem learning. According to Tang et al. (2021), this method promotes the development of oral fluency, enhances pronunciation, and boosts students' confidence in language use. Additionally, it fosters intercultural competence, enabling the students to understand the culture of another country better and develop practical communication skills in multicultural contexts.

However, language tandems in secondary education have been less explored, partly due to the logistical difficulties in coordinating schools in different countries and the need for adequate technological infrastructure. However, some studies have shown that implementing tandems in secondary education can greatly benefit students' motivation and language learning (Son et al., 2024).

Various projects have implemented strategies such as the linguistic tandem to improve language teaching in secondary education. In Spain, initiatives such as the Bilingual Program of the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training have promoted innovative methodologies for language teaching, including virtual exchanges and international collaborations.

At the European level, programs such as eTwinning, promoted by the European Commission, have demonstrated the potential of collaborative learning between students from

different countries through digital platforms. These projects have enabled students to enhance their communicative competence in a real-world interaction environment, aligning with the proposal of the linguistic tandem (Hernández Alvarado et al., 2023).

In the Irish context, initiatives such as the Languages Connect Strategy have promoted strategies to improve foreign language learning, highlighting the importance of interaction with native speakers and exposure to the language in authentic contexts. These policies have facilitated the creation of collaborative networks between Irish schools and those from other countries, setting a precedent for implementing the language tandem in this project.

This educational innovation project is based on this background to design a proposal that responds to the current challenges of language teaching in secondary education. Unlike traditional approaches, the language tandem initiative incorporates active methodologies, digital tools, and real interaction with native speakers, which makes it a project aligned with the latest trends in foreign language teaching.

In addition, by focusing on the context of secondary education, this project expands the scope of tandem learning, which has been more common in university settings. Combining digital learning, active methodologies, and international collaboration creates an innovative learning environment that models future language teaching initiatives (Lewis & Qian, 2021).

The project is grounded in a solid theoretical foundation and previous experiences demonstrating the effectiveness of learning through real-world communication. Its implementation addresses the students' linguistic competence needs and aligns with national and international educational policies that aim to modernize language teaching and promote intercultural competence.

2.3 Challenges and difficulties in language teaching in secondary education

Teaching foreign languages in secondary education faces several challenges, which are widely documented in the academic literature. Despite the growing importance of language skills in a globalized world, learners in many countries struggle to achieve sufficient competence in the target language. These challenges can be classified into different areas: methodological, motivational, technological, and socio-cultural.

One of the primary obstacles to language teaching in secondary education is the persistence of traditional approaches that explicitly teach grammatical rules and memorize vocabulary. Although the literature highlights the effectiveness of the communicative approach and task-based learning, many schools continue to employ methods that do not facilitate genuine interaction in the target language (Canals Soteras, 2020).

Language teaching in many educational curricula also relies on structuralist textbooks, limiting students' exposure to authentic communicative contexts. This lack of contextualization and real practice hinders the development of oral competence, which is essential for effective language acquisition.

The linguistic tandem proposed in this project seeks to overcome these limitations by introducing an approach based on interaction with native speakers, aligning with the recommendations of communicative teaching and active methodologies promoted by the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) (Council of Europe, 2001).

Another significant challenge in foreign language teaching is the lack of student motivation, which is a crucial factor influencing learning success. Studies have shown that interest in learning a FL decreases when students do not perceive its usefulness in everyday life or when teaching is based on mechanical and repetitive exercises (Canals Soteras, 2024).

In this sense, experiences of real contact with native speakers have proven to be a key factor in increasing motivation. The language tandem proposal adheres to this principle,

offering students a genuine motivation to communicate in the target language. The language tandem fosters this connection by allowing participants to experience the language in a real, socially relevant context (Kim, 2025).

Digital technologies have opened new opportunities for language teaching, but they also pose challenges regarding access, teacher training, and the availability of adequate infrastructure (Stickler et al., 2020). Although platforms such as Zoom, Microsoft Teams, or Google Meet have facilitated distance learning, not all schools have the necessary technological resources to implement them effectively (Schleicher, 2020).

Additionally, the time zone difference between Spain and Ireland can make it challenging to coordinate live sessions. To mitigate this problem, asynchronous learning strategies can be implemented, such as exchanging voice messages, emails, and recorded videos. Learning a foreign language involves not only the development of language skills but also the acquisition of intercultural skills. However, socio-cultural differences can challenge the interaction between students from different countries.

To reduce these barriers, the project must include preparatory sessions in which students receive information about the country's culture with which they will interact. Additionally, creating group dynamics and applying strategies to reduce communicative anxiety can help improve students' experience in the linguistic tandem.

3. METHOD

Foreign language (FL) learning is a complex process that requires dedication, formal instruction, and genuine opportunities to use the target language in authentic contexts. In this sense, the lack of exposure to real environments is one of the most significant challenges faced by the FL in CSE. In this context, this educational innovation project proposes the implementation of a linguistic tandem between a CSE high school in Granada (Spain), and an educational centre in Malahide (Ireland). This initiative aims to improve learners' language skills through interaction with native speakers.

These students are at a key stage of their psycho-evolutionary development. Students in CSE, typically between 12 and 16 years old, are in a transitional phase between childhood and adolescence, characterized by emotional, cognitive, and social growth. They have a greater capacity for abstract thinking and problem-solving regarding this transition. These skills facilitate the learning of a FL. However, their motivation and self-esteem also vary due to social, academic, and family pressures. Therefore, it is essential to employ active and participatory methodologies that motivate students and foster an interest in learning.

The high school in Granada is in an urban area with diverse social classes. Access to education is equitable, although socio-economic differences among students influence their learning opportunities outside the classroom. Some of these students have little to no experience in language immersion, which highlights the need for an innovative project such as the present language tandem.

On the other hand, the centre of Malahide is situated in a suburban area of County Dublin, characterized by a medium to high socio-economic status. The community values education and language learning, promoting Gaelic and facilitating the students' involvement in initiatives. However, the teaching of Spanish in Ireland faces challenges similar to those in Spain, such as the lack of exposure to native speakers and opportunities for actual communicative practice.

To implement the linguistic tandem, it is essential to identify the available resources and limitations that may affect the project's development. Among the resources are digital platforms facilitating communication between students from both centres, including tools for video calls, forums, and educational social networks. Likewise, the implementation of the

teaching staff is a crucial factor in ensuring the project's success, as their role will be to guide students in linguistic interactions.

Regarding physical resources, both centres have classrooms equipped with computers, internet access, and digital whiteboards. However, differences in infrastructure can affect the students' experiences. While the Malahide Centre has more modern facilities and resources, as well as access to advancements in educational technology, the high school in Granada may require a more robust technological infrastructure to ensure equitable participation (Redecker, 2023).

This innovation project is based on active methodologies that encourage students' participation in the acquisition and learning of languages. Project-based learning is adopted, in which students work on collaborative tasks (each person with their assigned responsibility) and cooperative tasks (working together on the same objective) using the target language (L2) in authentic contexts. Additionally, it incorporates gamification as a strategy to motivate students and make language practice more dynamic and engaging (Ellis, 2020).

From a curricular perspective, tandem activities are aligned with the learning objectives established in the educational programs of both centres. This ensures that participation in the project improves communication skills and contributes to meeting the academic standards of each country.

Beyond the development of language skills, the language tandem has a positive impact on students' intercultural competence, as the teaching of a language should not be limited exclusively to the acquisition of grammatical structures but should also include a deep understanding of the culture and social context in which the language is used. Interaction with native speakers enables students to develop greater intercultural sensitivity and understanding of customs and traditions and acquire practical communication skills in multicultural contexts.

Implementing this linguistic tandem between a high school in Granada and a school in Malahide represents an innovative and creative strategy to improve language teaching and learning in secondary education. By combining active methodological approaches with Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) and intercultural interaction, this project enhances students' knowledge of English and Spanish while promoting their personal and social development (O'Dowd, 2021). The continuous evaluation of the initiative's impact will enable the project to be adjusted and optimized, ensuring its success and potential replication in other educational contexts. Thus, this educational innovation project is expected to make a significant contribution to transforming FL teaching in both academic centres.

3.1. Research design

The language tandem project addresses different areas of improvement that contribute to optimizing the teaching-learning process and evaluating the educational environment. The first area for improvement is that the intervention will positively impact the acquisition of communicative skills. According to Dooly and O'Dowd (2021), language learning is reinforced through the use and production of one's language, which can be achieved through interaction with native speakers. With this tandem, students are expected to improve their fluency, pronunciation, listening comprehension, and oral expression, overcoming insufficient exposure to the language in the classroom.

Another aspect is that practice in an accurate and meaningful environment will increase the students' motivation, improving their confidence in communicating in the target language (FL). Pérez Cañado (2021) emphasizes that motivation is crucial to foreign language acquisition and can significantly influence learning success.

Integrating ICTs will improve student and centre interaction, allowing communication through collaborative platforms and educational social networks. Digitalizing the educational

process will modernize language teaching and provide new learning opportunities according to Fernández and Rodríguez (2021).

The centres' management will also be strengthened, as the implementation of this project requires coordination between the management team and the teaching staff of both centres (Holgado-Sáez & Díaz-Bravo, 2020). This will promote more collaborative management, new teaching strategies, and innovative methodologies that can be replicated at other educational levels.

Technological resources play an essential role, as although they possess essential technologies, expanding resources such as videoconferencing rooms, electronic devices, and access to educational platforms will further improve teaching-learning conditions. This investment will also be used for future exchange programs and other international projects (García Pérez, 2020).

Finally, this innovation project will strengthen the ties between the two educational communities and promote the centres' internationalization. It can also serve as a model for future collaboration with other institutions, both national and international, thereby enriching the academic offering.

On the other hand, the available resources and limitations must also be assessed. Among the existing resources are digital platforms facilitating communication between students from both centres, including video call tools, forums, and educational social networks. Likewise, the involvement of teachers is a key factor in guaranteeing the project's success, as they must guide students in their linguistic interactions (Guth & Helm, 2021).

However, some limitations must be considered. First, the time difference between Spain and Ireland can lead to difficulties in coordinating activities. Second, not all students will have the same level of motivation or competence in the foreign language, which could impact on the effectiveness of the linguistic tandem. In addition, the technological infrastructure of the centres must be adequate to allow fluid connection between participants, which requires an investment in technological resources if these are insufficient (Helm & Guth, 2020).

3.2. Objective

The main objective is to improve the linguistic and intercultural competence of secondary school students in the acquisition of a foreign language (FL) through an innovation project based on a linguistic tandem between a Compulsory Secondary Education (CSE) high school in Granada (Spain) and an educational centre in Malahide (Ireland). Learning a foreign language in CSE can present significant challenges, particularly in contexts with limited exposure to the FL. On many occasions, the predominant focus in the classroom is on grammatical instruction and memorizing rules, which can generate difficulties in oral production (speaking) and understanding real-life communicative situations (Hamilton, 2021). As mentioned in the previous sections, the lack of contact with native speakers and authentic experiences in which they can use the language limits the development of their skills.

To achieve this purpose, this proposed intervention is based on the idea that language learning is most effective when it occurs in an environment of natural interaction with native speakers. Muñoz and Sánchez (2023) noted that language acquisition occurs most significantly when the linguistic input is comprehensible and received in a genuine communicative context. However, in more traditional teaching methods, students often lack these opportunities, affecting their fluency and confidence in using the foreign language.

This innovation project aims to bridge this gap by creating a two-way communication context in which Spanish and Irish students can enhance their language proficiency through direct contact and mutual learning. It also addresses another approach that goes beyond the development of language skills, focusing on the intercultural component since language

learning is intrinsically linked to the socio-cultural context (Stickler et al., 2020). As described above, language teaching in the current educational system often overlooks this fact, which creates difficulties in understanding the pragmatic and sociolinguistic aspects. The tandem will promote knowledge and appreciation of diversity while improving the students' communicative competence.

This educational innovation project is also based on transforming language teaching through more active and dynamic methodologies. The proposal incorporates strategies such as project-based learning and gamification, which will facilitate the motivation and commitment of students. In traditional education, learning a foreign language is often perceived as a tedious and impractical academic task, diminishing students' interest and confidence in their communication skills. However, by introducing an experiential approach based on real interaction, students are expected to become more actively involved in the learning process and to perceive language as a valuable and necessary tool for communication.

Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) will also be crucial in the project's execution. Digital platforms will enable students to participate in video calls, forums, and other interactive activities without physical travel. In this sense, technology will serve as a bridge to connect students from both schools, facilitating a language immersion experience without requiring them to leave the classroom. Schleicher (2020) noted that using digital tools in language learning can enhance motivation and provide access to a broader range of resources, ultimately contributing to more effective and flexible teaching.

Regarding its educational impact, this intervention is expected to have a positive effect on the students' academic performance as well as their personal and social development. Improving students' oral competence and motivation will be key indicators to measure the project's success. Ellis (2020) emphasizes that learning a FL entails acquiring language skills and developing cognitive skills, such as problem-solving and creativity. Likewise, contact with native speakers and participation in intercultural activities can foster empathy and respect for other cultures, which are essential aspects of comprehensive student education.

In conclusion, this work proposes an innovative intervention to transform language teaching in secondary education through a communicative and culturally enriching approach. The linguistic tandem between the high school in Granada and the school in Malahide will not only improve the students' linguistic competence but also develop their intercultural competence, motivation, and confidence in language use.

4. INNOVATION PROJECT

Developing an innovation project in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) for Spanish learners, and Spanish as a Foreign Language (ELE) for Irish learners involves structured planning that ensures the implementation of new methodologies, tools, or approaches to optimize the teaching and learning process. Innovation in education must respond to specific needs detected in the classroom and be based on solid pedagogical models that favour language acquisition effectively and meaningfully.

To achieve this, it is essential to divide the process into different phases: initiation, application or development, and evaluation. Each of these stages enables the establishment of clear objectives, coordination of the involved agents, definition of methodological strategies, and assessment of the impact of innovation on student learning.

The project's foundations are established in the initiation phase, defining specific objectives based on a previously described general purpose. These objectives must be aligned with the educational context's needs and measurable to evaluate their effectiveness later (García-Pérez, 2020). It is essential to conduct a prior diagnosis that identifies the primary

challenges in teaching Spanish as a foreign language, such as the lack of oral interaction in the classroom, low student motivation, or the need to incorporate digital technologies into learning.

Based on this analysis, a schedule of activities is designed that marks the key milestones of the project's implementation, from planning to evaluation. The available organizational and didactic resources were identified during this phase, including educational materials, technological tools, and the necessary infrastructure to implement the proposal. The agents involved in the process were also determined, including teachers, pedagogical coordinators, specialists in educational technology, families, and the students.

The application or development phase is when the necessary actions are implemented to achieve the project's objectives. Here, we outline the approach to introducing innovation in the EFL classroom, detailing the innovative elements and activities that underpin the teaching process. This phase must adopt a methodological strategy consistent with the didactic principles of EFL, using approaches such as project-based learning, gamification, interactive digital tools, or multisensory teaching.

Additionally, it is essential to design activities that encourage student participation and dynamically facilitate language acquisition. A fundamental aspect of this phase is the coordination between the agents involved, mainly when the project necessitates collaboration among educational institutions, government entities, or sectors specializing in language teaching. Inter-institutional cooperation strengthens innovation's impact and ensures its long-term viability, thereby maintaining effective communication channels between participants.

Finally, the evaluation phase of the project aims to measure the impact of innovation on student learning and determine to what extent the established objectives have been achieved. To this end, various assessment instruments have been employed, including satisfaction surveys, language performance tests, classroom observations, and data analysis on student participation (García Pérez, 2020).

The evaluation should focus on the results and the implementation process, identifying potential areas for improvement and adjusting strategies based on the findings obtained. Additionally, it is advisable to adopt a continuous evaluation approach that enables adjustments throughout the project's development, ensuring its effectiveness.

To summarize, an innovation project in teaching Spanish as a FL should be structured into well-defined phases that facilitate its planning, execution, and evaluation. Incorporating new methodologies and tools must respond to the specific needs of the educational context and guarantee substantial improvement in language acquisition. Collaboration between the agents involved and appropriate methodological strategies are key elements for the success of innovation. Likewise, the rigorous evaluation of the project allows its effectiveness to be validated and the necessary improvements to be made to optimize its impact on student learning.

4.1. Initiation phase

The initiation phase is a fundamental pillar in designing and developing the linguistic tandem innovation project between a high school in Granada and a school in Malahide. At this point, specific objectives are established, the necessary resources are identified, and a detailed schedule is created to ensure the project's viability and success. According to O'Dowd (2021), meticulous planning is crucial for participants in virtual exchange projects to achieve meaningful learning and develop intercultural competencies. To ensure the correct implementation of the project and the protection of students, the collaboration agreement and informed consent models were used.

First, defining specific objectives enables the specification of the linguistic tandem's purpose within the educational innovation framework. The primary objective is to enhance

communicative competence in Spanish and English through authentic participant interaction. To this end, goals are pursued, including promoting linguistic immersion in authentic contexts, developing intercultural competencies, enhancing motivation and autonomy in language learning, and evaluating the impact of the applied methodology. Previous studies on tele-collaboration in language teaching, such as those by Guth and Helm (2021), highlight the importance of clearly setting these objectives to ensure that educational innovation has a tangible impact on students.

The project timeline is divided into three key phases: planning, implementation, and evaluation. In the initial phase, which lasts approximately three months, agreements are established with the high school of Granada and the school of Malahide, the participating groups are defined, and materials are adapted to meet the project's needs. In parallel, training is provided to teachers and students on using digital tools to facilitate communication and collaboration (Stickler et al., 2020).

Then, during the implementation phase, which could span from the fourth to the twelfth month, language tandem sessions were developed through structured activities, and continuous monitoring of the learning process was conducted. This stage is crucial because guided interaction in tele-collaboration environments can significantly enhance the development of language skills. Finally, the evaluation and dissemination phase, which spans the last three months, focuses on analysing the results through surveys, interviews, and linguistic tests, allowing the project's impact to be assessed and proposing improvements for future editions.

Another essential aspect in the initiation phase is identifying organizational and didactic resources and the involvement of various agents in the project's development. According to recent studies, the participation of multiple stakeholders, including teaching teams, students, families, and educational institutions, is crucial to the success of exchange programs (O'Dowd, 2021). The role of teachers is not only limited to facilitating learning but also to acting as cultural mediators and designers of meaningful learning experiences. Additionally, family involvement can boost student motivation and ensure a more significant commitment to the project.

In terms of organizational-didactic procedures, the use of active methodologies, such as project-based learning (PBL) and cooperative learning, is essential to maximize the benefits of the linguistic tandem. Integrating digital tools, such as video conferencing, forums, and collaborative learning platforms, facilitates participant interaction and enables effective monitoring of each student's progress (Stickler et al., 2020). Additionally, the design of structured activities, which combines oral and written interaction and cultural activities, contributes to more dynamic and contextualized learning, aligning with the best practices identified in the literature on virtual exchange (Guth & Helm, 2021).

In conclusion, the initiation phase of the language tandem project between Granada and Malahide lays the foundations for an innovative and effective learning experience. Rigorous planning, establishing clear and achievable objectives, involving various agents, and using appropriate methodologies ensure that the language exchange improves the participants' competence in Spanish and English and promotes intercultural understanding and motivation for learning foreign languages.

4.2. Project implementation or development phase

The application phase is the central pillar of the linguistic tandem project between the high school of Granada and the school of Malahide. At this point, the necessary actions are taken to meet the objectives, ensuring that educational innovation is effectively integrated into the ELE and EFL classrooms. According to Helm and Guth (2020), the implementation of virtual

exchanges should follow a structured and adaptable approach to maximize their impact on language learning and intercultural training.

One key aspect of this phase is the introduction of innovation within the language teaching curriculum in both schools. The innovation in this project is based on the combination of telecollaboration with active learning methodologies, which allows students to develop their language skills through authentic interactions.

The main innovative element lies in integrating telecollaboration as a methodological tool. Students from the high school of Granada and the school of Malahide participate in weekly language tandem sessions through videoconferences and interactive platforms. These sessions are organized around themed activities to promote meaningful communication and experiential learning. Research by O'Dowd (2021) highlights that well-structured virtual exchanges can foster greater autonomy in education and enhance oral fluency in informal and collaborative learning contexts.

Specific actions that underpin innovation include planning interactive activities, such as discussions on cultural issues, paired problem-solving, simulations of everyday situations, and collaborative projects. Additionally, asynchronous discussion forums were implemented, allowing students to continue interacting outside the live sessions. These strategies align with the recommendations of Stickler et al. (2020), who suggest that combining synchronous and asynchronous interactions in virtual environments optimizes language learning.

Regarding methodology, the project adopts a communicative approach with a strong orientation towards Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT). According to Ellis (2020), this approach is efficient in contexts of language exchange, as it enables students to use the target language in an authentic and contextually relevant manner. In addition, Project-Based Learning (PBL) is incorporated, where students create bilingual digital content, such as podcasts, blogs, or videos, which reflect the cultural aspects of Spain and Ireland. This methodology strengthens language skills and fosters digital competencies and critical thinking skills.

A crucial aspect of the implementation phase is the progressive introduction of innovative resources in specific learning situations. For example, one of the first activities involves a video conference in which students introduce themselves and share experiences about their respective cities. This initial interaction helps break the ice and establishes an environment of trust, which is critical to the exchange's success (O'Dowd, 2021). Subsequently, more complex tasks, such as discussions on cultural differences or the joint production of educational materials, are introduced following a structured pedagogical progression.

The project implementation also requires collaboration with various actors, especially in the context of international educational innovation. Inter- and intra-institutional coordination is key to ensuring the success of the exchange. In this sense, teachers act as facilitators and mediators, ensuring that the activities are accessible and beneficial to all participants. In addition, the participation of families and other external stakeholders, such as cultural institutions and language teaching experts, is encouraged to enrich the learning experience. According to Dooly and Sadler (2021), cooperation between different educational actors strengthens the sustainability of tele-collaboration projects and their long-term impact.

Another essential element is adapting the project to the students' needs and characteristics. Monitoring and adjustment mechanisms are established to ensure that activities are inclusive and accessible. For example, subtitles in video conferences are permitted to enhance comprehension, and activities are designed to cater to different levels of language proficiency. These strategies coincide with the best practices identified by Guth and Helm (2021), who underline the importance of flexibility and personalization in online learning projects.

Finally, the implementation phase of the language tandem project between the high school of Granada and the school of Malahide materializes educational innovation through active methodologies and the strategic use of tele-collaboration. The combination of live interaction, collaborative work, and teaching support ensures that participants improve their competence in the target language and develop key intercultural and digital skills for the 21st century. As Stickler et al. (2020) highlight, effectively integrating technology into language learning requires careful planning and flexible implementation, ensuring that all learners can benefit from the experience.

5. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The evaluation phase is a crucial component in any educational innovation project, as it enables the impact of the proposal to be measured, areas for improvement to be identified, and the sustainability of the initiative to be ensured. In the case of the linguistic tandem between the high school of Granada and the school of Malahide, the assessment should not only focus on the linguistic results of the students but also on the methodological, technological, and socio-emotional aspects. According to O'Dowd (2021), evaluating virtual exchanges requires integrating quantitative and qualitative metrics to comprehensively understand learning and the student experience.

The evaluation of the project is structured into three fundamental levels: evaluation of the students' learning, assessment of the implementation process, and evaluation of the project's general impact on the educational community. Specific tools and strategies are used for each level to analyse the data rigorously and with a well-founded approach.

Various assessment strategies are applied to determine whether the linguistic and communicative objectives have been achieved. One of the primary tools is using language proficiency tests before and after the exchange to measure the evolution of skills in the target language. According to Ellis (2020), performance-based assessments are particularly relevant in communicative learning contexts as they evaluate linguistic fluency, accuracy, and complexity in real-world situations.

In addition to traditional tests, evaluation rubrics are used to analyse interactions in video conferences, discussion forums, and collaborative projects. These rubrics include criteria such as discursive coherence, lexical richness, pronunciation, and interaction in the target language. Recent studies, such as those of Stickler et al. (2020), suggest that analysing oral and written production samples in virtual exchanges can provide valuable data on student progress.

Another key method is self-assessment and co-assessment. Participants completed reflective questionnaires at the end of each phase of the project, assessing their progress and that of their peers. This strategy fosters autonomy and metacognitive awareness, two fundamental aspects of language learning (Dooly & Sadler, 2021).

To guarantee an objective and formative assessment of the development of students in the language tandem project, several specific rubrics have been designed: one for oral communicative competence, another for intercultural competence, one for collaborative work and another for motivation and autonomy. These tools will make it possible to comprehensively assess the progress of students in the different areas of learning.

Evaluating the project's implementation from organizational and methodological perspectives is necessary to ensure its effectiveness. Structured observations of the exchange sessions were conducted using checklists that assessed the dynamics of the interactions, student participation, and the adequacy of the activities. According to Guth and Helm (2021), direct observation and analysis of recordings can help detect potential communication difficulties and adjust the methodology accordingly.

Discussion groups are also organized with teachers and students to gather feedback on the project's development. These sessions allow for identifying strengths and weaknesses in the implementation and adjusting aspects such as workload, participant motivation, and technology integration. As Bueno Reina and Alvarado Martínez (2022) suggest, continuous formative assessment is crucial in telecollaboration projects as it enables flexible adaptation to emerging needs.

Another crucial aspect in evaluating the process is analysing its technological use. Data were collected on the accessibility, usability, and effectiveness of the digital platforms used. Helm and Guth (2020) noted that an essential criterion is the ease of navigation and fluid interaction between participants. In the event of recurring technical issues, adjustments are made to enhance the user experience.

Beyond the individual results, the project's impact on the educational community is also analysed. This analysis includes the perceptions of teachers and families regarding the usefulness of the linguistic tandem and its effects on student motivation. Surveys were conducted with the various agents involved to gauge their level of satisfaction and gather suggestions for future editions.

Another factor to consider is the project's sustainability. Whether the initiative can be sustained over time and replicated in other educational contexts is reviewed. According to Hamilton (2021), successful tele-collaboration projects often integrate continuity mechanisms, such as creating reusable teaching materials and consolidating alliances between institutions.

Finally, evaluation reports that compile the most relevant findings and recommendations for future editions of the language tandem are prepared. These reports are shared with teaching teams and educational administrations, ensuring the dissemination of good practices and strengthening the virtual exchange model.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Implementing the linguistic tandem between students in Spain and Ireland could be an innovative strategy that overcomes the limitations of traditional methods focused on grammar and memorization by offering a real and meaningful communicative experience. This intervention will allow learners to be exposed to an authentic linguistic environment, favouring not only the improvement of their oral and written skills but also the development of intercultural competence, an aspect often relegated in conventional language teaching. Direct interaction with native speakers will increase students' motivation and self-confidence, which are key elements for effective learning.

By contrasting this experience with traditional exchange programs, the virtual language tandem is positioned as a more accessible, sustainable, and scalable alternative, which eliminates economic and logistical barriers, democratizing access to linguistic and cultural immersion. However, inequalities still may appear regarding access to and use of the necessary technologies, especially among the participating centres, which underlines the importance of equitable technological endowment and digital training to maximize the project's impact. Similarly, the flexible adaptation of the program to the specific needs of each educational context proves to be an essential factor for its success.

From an innovative perspective, the project will systematically integrate intercultural competence into didactic programming and assessment, significantly advancing over most current curricula that tend to ignore this dimension. This fact not only facilitates the understanding and appreciation of the customs and lifestyles of the interlocutor community but also contributes to the formation of global citizens prepared to function in multicultural environments. In short, the linguistic tandem represents an effective bridge for linguistic and

cultural integration, transforming language teaching and offering a replicable model that responds to the contemporary challenges of foreign language education.

Based on the analysis of the intervention developed and the challenges detected during its development, various lines of innovation are opened that can promote the improvement and evolution of foreign language learning and intercultural competence in educational contexts. One of the most relevant proposals is to deepen the personalization of the linguistic tandem, incorporating artificial intelligence and data analysis tools to dynamically adapt content, pairings, and activities to each student's interests, needs, and proficiency levels. This innovation would not only optimize the learning process but also address diversity and promote inclusion, thereby overcoming the limitations of current models.

In parallel, integrating hybrid methodologies that combine face-to-face and virtual learning opens new possibilities to enrich the tandem experience. For example, organizing one-off face-to-face meetings, intercultural workshops, or joint collaborative projects, either physically or through virtual reality, can strengthen the bonds between participants and enhance experiential learning. Contrasting this proposal with the exclusively virtual model allows us to identify the advantages and challenges. While virtual democratizes access and reduces costs, face-to-face provides an emotional and social dimension that is difficult to replicate remotely.

Another line of prospective innovation focuses on formative and competency assessment, incorporating rubrics and digital portfolios that include linguistic progress, the development of intercultural skills, critical reflection, and the ability to work collaboratively. Compared to traditional assessments, this approach makes it possible to give visibility to more complex and transversal learning, aligned with the demands of today's society. In addition, creating virtual learning communities, which include families, teachers, and external agents (universities, companies, and cultural associations), can enrich the educational ecosystem and open new opportunities for exchange and collaboration beyond the classroom.

7. BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abdel Latif, O.I. (2024). Using Genre-Based Approach for Developing Faculty of Education English Majors' Expository Writing and Environmental Awareness. *Journal of Research in Curriculum Instruction and Educational Technology*, 10(2), 295-344. <https://doi.org/10.21608/jrciet.2024.363676>
- Bolívar Botía, A. (2021). La autonomía del profesorado y el liderazgo escolar en los centros educativos. *Revista de Educación*, 394, 11-33. <https://doi.org/10.4438/1988-592X-RE-2021-394-490>
- Bueno Reyna, P.A. & Alvarado Martínez, E. (2022). El uso de tandems virtuales como herramienta para la motivación del aprendizaje del inglés como lengua extranjera. *Lengua y Cultura*, 3(6), 111-120. <https://doi.org/10.29057/lc.v3i6.8585>
- Canals Soteras, L. (2024). "It was like a mental Erasmus!" Perceptions of language learning and intercultural understanding in an e-tandem virtual exchange. *Journal of Virtual Exchange*, 7, 60-83. <https://doi.org/10.21827/jve.7.41056>
- Canals Soteras, L. (2020). The effects of virtual exchanges on oral skills and motivation. *Language Learning & Technology*, 24(3), 103-119.
- Dooly, M. & Sadler, R. (2021). Online language learning in tandem: Design, implementation, and outcomes. *Language Learning & Technology*, 25(2), 103-123.
- Ellis, R. (2020). *Task-Based Language Teaching: Theory and Practice*. Cambridge University Press.
- Elo, J. & Pörn, M. (2021). Challenges of implementing authenticity of tandem learning in formal language education. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 24(6), 771-784. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2018.1516188>
- European Commission. (2021). *Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027): Resetting education and training for the digital age*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2021). *Strategic Framework for European Cooperation in Education and Training to 2030*.
- Eurydice. (2022). *Structural indicators for monitoring education and training systems in Europe*. Publications Office of the European Union.

- Freiermuth, M. R. & Huang, H. C. (2021). Zooming across cultures: Can a telecollaborative video exchange between language learning partners further the development of intercultural competences? *Foreign Language Annals*, 54(1), 185-206. <https://doi.org/10.1111/flan.12504>
- García Pérez, D. (2020). Design and evaluation of innovation projects in Spanish as a foreign language: a practical approach. *Journal of Educational Innovation*, 25(3), 34-52.
- Green, A. (2020). *Education and State Formation: Europe, East Asia and the USA*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Guth, S. & Helm, F. (2021). *Virtual Exchange in the Second Language Classroom: A Pedagogical Guide*. Open Book Publishers.
- Haleem, A., Javaid, M., Qadri, M.A. & Suman, R. (2022). Understanding the role of digital technologies in education: A review. *Sustainable Operations and Computers*, 3, 275-285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susoc.2022.05.004>
- Hamilton, D. (2021). *A History of Organised Schooling: Social and Intellectual Perspectives*. Routledge.
- Helm, F. & Guth, S. (2020). Developing intercultural communicative competence through online exchanges. *Journal of Language and Intercultural Communication*, 20(1), 25-40.
- Hernández Alvarado, M. G., Hidalgo Avilés, H. & Espinos Butrón, N. A. (2023). Promoting the development of autonomy in the context of teletandem in language teacher education. *The ESPecialist*, 43(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.23925/2318-7115.2022v43i1a15>
- Holgado Sáez, C. & Díaz Bravo, R. (Eds.). (2020). *Enseñanza-aprendizaje de lenguas en la era digital: Investigación e innovación educativa*. Editorial Comares.
- Isaí Serrato, D. & Padilla Rodríguez, B.C. (2020). Academic e-tandems as a strategy for English language learning in a Mexican university. *Open Praxis*, 12(3), 417-424. <https://doi.org/10.5944/openpraxis.12.3.1099>
- Krashen, S. (1982). *Principles and Practice in Second Language Acquisition*. Pergamon Press.
- Kim, J.E. (2025). Application and evaluation of Spanish-Korean e-tandem learning. *Iberoamérica*, 27(1), 35-65. <https://doi.org/10.19058/iberoamerica.2025.6.27.1.35>
- Lewis, T. & Qian, K. (2021) Designing and supporting virtual exchange: The case of Chinese-English e-Tandem. *Modern Languages Open*, 19(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.3828/mlo.v0i0.372>
- Martínez Flor, A. & Usó Juan, E. (2022). La interacción oral en el aprendizaje de lenguas extranjeras: retos y oportunidades. *Didáctica. Lengua y Literatura*, 34, 45–62. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=8390123>
- O'Dowd, R. (2021). Virtual exchange: Moving forward into the next decade. *Journal of E-Learning and Digital Learning*, 18(2), 78-95. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2021.1902201>
- Pérez Cañado, M.L. (2021). Competencia intercultural y enseñanza de lenguas extranjeras: Estado de la cuestión y propuestas didácticas. *Tejuelo*, 33, 9–33. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=8123456>
- Redecker, C. (2023). *Digital education strategies: Building digital capacity in teacher education*. European Commission.
- Royo Vela, M., Haba Oisca, J. & Martínez Ruiz, M.P. (2023). Gamificación y aprendizaje de lenguas extranjeras: una revisión sistemática. *Educación XX1*, 26(2), 235–256. <https://doi.org/10.5944/educxx1.33834>
- Schleicher, A. (2020). *The impact of digitalisation on education systems*. OECD iLibrary.
- Son, B.G., Yuan, X. & Guo, X. (2024). E-tandem learning and autonomous learning: Learners' perceptions of benefits and challenges. *Australian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 261-266. <https://doi.org/10.29140/9780648184485-39>
- Stickler, U., Hampel, R. & Emke, M. (2020). A developmental framework for online language teaching skills. *Australian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 3(1), 133-151. <https://doi.org/10.29140/ajal.v3n1.271>
- Tang, J., Kan, Q., Wang, N. & Hu, X. (2021). Exploring language learning and corrective feedback in an eTandem project. *Journal of China Computer-Assisted Language Learning*, 1(1), 110-144. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jccall-2021-2005>
- Topal, I. H. (2024). Tandem language exchange application: A telecollaborative experience of linguistic and cultural exchange. *Journal of Digital Educational Technology*, 4(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.30935/jdet/14298>
- Wardak, M. (2024). It's Tandem, not Tinder! Interrogating Authenticity and Trustworthiness of Language Exchange Applications in Adult Learners: A Central Asian and Middle Eastern Perspective. *World Journal of English Language*, 14(2), 293-309. <https://doi.org/10.5430/wjel.v14n2p293>